

Analyzing Repetitive DNA Involved in Tissue Regeneration in Echinoderms

Gerald Branden Mabe

Poster Narrative

Echinoderms are phylogenetically related to humans and can undergo whole-body regeneration (WBR) when exposed to trauma (Mashanov *et al.*, 2012). Echinoderms such as *Sclerodactyla briareus* (sea cucumber) and *Ophioderma brevispina* (brittle star) have great regenerative potential, but the precise molecular mechanisms involved in their WBR are unknown (Mashanov *et al.*, 2012). As such, a collaborative effort led by Dr. Daniel Janies (UNC Charlotte) and Dr. Vladimir Mashanov (Wake Forest University Institute for Regenerative Medicine) and financed by the NIH (project no. 1R15GM128066-01) is aiming to build the foundations towards making *O. brevispina* and *S. briareus* new models in tissue regeneration. Unfortunately, there is a lack of closely-related reference genomes to work with, and the *de novo* assemblies of the brittle star and the sea cucumber are highly fragmented, partially due to the repetitive DNA elements in their genomes (Mashanov *et al.*, 2014). Repetitive elements are sequences of nucleotides that repeat themselves throughout the genome, such as transposable elements (Burns, 2020). At the same time that they hamper *de novo* assemblies of non-model genomes, it has been hypothesized that they play a role in tissue regeneration (Mashanov *et al.*, *in press*).

Quantification and categorization of repetitive DNA elements are, therefore, of special interest in the comparative genomics of echinoderms. However, we lack a classification system that can categorize different types of repeats, which hampers downstream analysis including the quantification of repeats in the absence of complete chromosome assemblies. To tackle this problem, we selected the complete chromosome assembly of the common starfish *Asterias rubens* (version assembly_MT_rockefeller from 7 December 2019, available at vgp.github.io/genomeark/Asterias_rubens) as a model to improve on a classification system for repetitive DNA elements that is based on the classification system of transposable elements (TEs) of Wicker *et al.* (2007). We proposed modifications that allow the classification of TEs and other repeats simultaneously. The improved system (1) detaches the biological meaning from the hierarchical levels of classification so that the biological meaning is attached to the names of each group only; (2) includes a new upper level, Phylum, that divides TEs from other elements; (3) classifies non-LTR retrotransposons as an Order and classifies LINEs as a Family; (4) alters the label "Class" to increase clarity and simplicity; (5) introduces clear formatting rules naming repeats; and (6) uses the classification "Unknown" when more specific labels have been determined but preceding levels of classification have not. We demonstrate how our improved classification system may be applied using the genome of *A. rubens* as an example.

The improved classification system for repetitive elements allows for more efficient comparisons and greater insights into their phylogeny, function, and quantification, especially

concerning their role in tissue regeneration in echinoderms. By better understanding repetitive elements and their evolution in echinoderms and other animals, we may uncover information that will aid in the creation of regenerative technologies in humans. In addition, the classification system acts as a foundation for more improvements in the future.

References

- Burns, K. H. (2020). Our Conflict with Transposable Elements and Its Implications for Human Disease. *Annual Review of Pathology: Mechanisms of Disease*, **15**, 51-70.
- Mashanov, V. S., Zueva, O. R., & Garcia-Arrarás, J. E. (2012). Expression of Wnt9, TCTP, and Bmp1/Tll in sea cucumber visceral regeneration. *Gene Expression Patterns*, **12(1-2)**, 24-35.
- Mashanov, V. S., Zueva, O. R., & García-Arrarás, J. E. (2014). Transcriptomic changes during regeneration of the central nervous system in an echinoderm. *BMC Genomics*, **15(1)**, 357.
- Mashanov, V. S. Akiona, J., Khoury, M., Ferrier, J., Reid, R., Machado, D. J., Zueva, O., Janies, D. A. (*in press*). Active Notch signaling is required for arm regeneration in a brittle star. *PLOS ONE*. Available at *BioRxiv*, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2019.12.13.875401>.
- Wicker, T., Sabot, F., Hua-Van, A., Bennetzen, J. L., *et al.* (2007). A unified classification system for eukaryotic transposable elements. *Nature Reviews Genetics*, **8(12)**, 973-982.